

Time Dependent Harmonic Oscillator with a Time-Dependent Force and Flux Balance

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The time-dependent Schrodinger problem of an oscillator $.5kx^2$ together with the additional potential $-x f(t)$, where $f(t)$ is a function of time (often periodic), has already been solved in the literature (1). The solution involves a variable transformation $y = x - b(t)$, where $b(t)$ is a function of time which will turn out to be related to $f(t)$ and $W(x,t) = \exp(i y \frac{d}{dt} b(t)) W_{osc}(y) \exp(i E_{osc} t)$. This yields an oscillator type time dependent equation with a term $q(t) W_{osc}(y)$ which can be removed by using $W_{osc}(y) \exp(i c(t))$. $W_{osc}(y)$ is the oscillator wavefunction with the space-time variable y and E_{osc} the usual oscillator energy levels. Thus, by using the variable transformation together with $W(x,t) = W_{osc}(x) \exp(i E_{osc} t) g(x,t)$ (i.e. a product of factors) one can obtain an "time-independent like" Schrodinger equation in y (after performing one more transformation $W_{osc}(y) \exp(i c(t))$).

In a previous note (2), we argued that if one writes a wavefunction as $W(x) = W_0(x)q(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction, one obtains a time-independent Schrodinger equation for $W_0(x)$, which contains $V(x)$, and a second eigenvalue equation coupling $W_0(x)$ and $q(x)$ with an eigenvalue equal to $E - E_0$. In particular, it is the time flux $[d/dt W(x,t)]/W(x,t)$ which becomes linked with $q(x)$ and the spatial flux $[d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$.

In (3), we argued that bound state quantum mechanics contains two velocities $v(x)$, the classical velocity and $u(x)/m = [d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$ and that each behave differently. For example, $v(x)$ behaves according to Newton's law, while $u(x)/m$ does not (except for the oscillator ground state).

In this note, we try to apply these two ideas to the case of the oscillator with the time-dependent extra potential $x f(t)$. We see that writing $W(x,t)$ as a product (after the variable change) leads to two sets equation, one being a time-independent like equation for the oscillator and the other linking $u(x)/m$ to a portion of time flux $[d/dt W(x,t)]/W(x,t) |x \text{ constant}$. In this case, the time flux is directly related to $d/dx [W^*(x,t)W(x,t)]$ i.e. the physical density. Thus, a change in physical density in time is related to a change in physical density in space. Thus, two physical processes, it seems, are occurring. One is the $W_{osc}(y)$ resonance (albeit it a strange one because $y = x + b(t)$) and the second flux coupling with $\exp(i b(t) y)$, part of the oscillator potential and part of the additional potential $-x f(t)$. Given that the problem has been mathematically solved already in the literature (1), our objective is to attempt to see if there is physical meaning in terms of ideas we have presented in previous notes, namely flux, the notion of a product wavefunction leading to a separate resonance type of reaction and double resonances.

Oscillator Potential together with Additional $-x f(t)$ Potential

The time-dependent Schrodinger equation for this problem may be written (with $\hbar = 1$) as:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) + .5k x^2 W(x,t) - x f(t) W(x,t) \quad ((1))$$

In solving this problem, a couple of ideas immediately appear. First, if $f(t)=\text{constant}$, one would have a time-independent equation with a shifted x i.e. $y= x + b$. Secondly, the transformation $W(x,t)= \exp(i x g(t)) Wa(x,t)$ with $d/dt g(t) = -f(t)$ would allow one to eliminate $x f(t) W(x,t)$ on the RHS, but would also lead to a piece of time flux: $i \exp(i x g(t)) d/dt Wa(x,t)$ where $Wa(x,t)$ is the remaining part of the wavefunction. In the term $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x,t)$, the product wavefunction form leads to a term $2 i g(t) d/dx Wa(x,t)$. If one uses a variable transformation $y= x- b(t)$, the piece of time flux has the same form as the spatial flux and the two may cancel. We argue already at this point that time and spatial fluxes represent physical processes which are being linked with part of the $x f(t)$ potential and part of the oscillator potential. This allows $Wa(x,t)=Wa(y,t)$ to satisfy a Schrodinger equation which may be converted into a time-independent like one with y taking the place of the usually x (spatial only) variable after one performs one more transformation $\exp(i c(t)) Wa(y,t)$ to remove pure time pieces $z(t)Wa(y,t)$. Given that this approach is taken, one must check the energy associated with the flux equation as the time-independent Schrodinger like one yields the usual time-independent values of $E=.5 \text{sqrt}(k/m) (n+.5)$.

Flux Ideas

For a bound state Schrodinger equation, one may write, as in (2), the wavefunction as $W(x)=Wo(x)Hn(x)$ (like the case of the oscillator). $Wo(x)$ satisfies the usual time-independent Schrodinger equation with a direct appearance of $V(x)$, but $Hn(x)$ couples with $Wo(x)$ to create an eigenvalue equation which stems only from the $-1/2m d/dx d/dx$ kinetic energy term i.e.:

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx Hn(x) -1/m [d/dx Wo(x)]/Wo(x) d/dx Hn(x) = E1 Hn(x) \quad ((2))$$

One may note that ((2)) contains the flux $u(x)/m$ associated with $Wo(x)$ coupling with $Hn(x)$ to create an eigenvalue equation. $E1 Hn(x)$ is obtained from $i d/dt \exp(iE1t) Hn(x)$, so it is a time flux (which happens to reduce to $E1 \exp(iE1t) Hn(x)$). Thus, there are two equations, one the regular time-independent Schrodinger equation, and the second linking space flux to time flux which leads to another eigenvalue resonance problem. Thus, there is a double resonance. In addition, both processes may be physical, as $Wo(x)$ represents a physical resonance, that of the ground state, and in the case of the oscillator ((2)) is related to a quanta of energy $\hbar w$ which represents a phonon, for example.

A similar scenario seems to exist for the oscillator with an additional potential of $-x f(t)$. One introduces a variable change $y=x-b(t)$ so that one may link the space flux of $Wa(y)$ to time flux of $Wa(y)$. In this case, however, part of the potential $x f(t)$ as well as part of the oscillator potential $.5kx*x$ are involved and (a part of the) time flux does not yield $E1 Hn(x)$, but rather cancels the space flux. Thus, there are again two equations:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dx} \psi(y,t) + .5ky^2 \psi(y,t) + c(t) \psi(y,t) = E \psi(y,t) \text{ where } \psi(y,t) = \psi(y) \exp(iEt) \quad ((3))$$

The $c(t) \psi(y,t)$ term may be eliminated by replacing $\psi(y)$ with $\psi(y) \exp(-i \int c(t) dt)$ such that $\frac{d}{dt} \psi(y,t) = c(t) \psi(y,t)$.

And

$$-m \psi(y,t) \left[\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dx} \psi(y,t) \right] - i \left[\frac{d}{dt} \int c(t) dt \right] \frac{d}{dy} \psi(y,t) = (-1/2) \hbar^2 \left[\frac{d}{dx} \psi(y,t) \right] \frac{d}{dy} \psi(y,t) - f(t) \psi(y,t) + .5k \int c(t) dt \psi(y,t) \quad ((4))$$

By performing the first transformation $\exp[i \int c(t) dt]$ one obtains cancellation of time and space flux as well as the elimination of the presence of y in the $y f(t)$ piece and $k y^2$ piece. Thus, one has:

$$m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dx} \psi(y,t) = y f(t) - k \int c(t) dt \psi(y,t) \quad ((4b)) \text{ with } y \text{ canceling out.}$$

It may be noted that in order to have the “ y ” cancel, one had to assign the purely time dependent potential terms to ((3)). If they had been associated with ((4)), one would have a mix of x and t which would be problematic to solve.

It may be noted that ((4)) involves the time flux, space flux, $y f(t)$ (i.e. part of the time potential) and $.5k \int c(t) dt$ (part of the oscillator potential). Equation ((3)) (which will become the time independent Schrodinger equation, also involves part of the oscillator potential i.e. $.5k y^2$ and part of the time potential i.e. $b(t) f(t)$. This piece of potential contains no “ x ” and so is not associated with a force. A phase transformation may eliminate it together with any other pure time pieces (multiplied by $\psi(y,t)$).

This, however, leaves a pure function of t , namely $c(t)$ in ((3)). This can be removed by noting that:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \int c(t) dt) = c(t) \text{ where } \int c(t) dt = \int_0^t c(t') dt' \quad ((5))$$

Physical Process of the Second Equation

In ((4)), even though both sides cancel, it seems one should consider the physical process related. The time flux linked to $\frac{d}{dx} \psi(y,t)$ on the LHS is equivalent to $\frac{d}{dt} [\psi(y) \psi(y)]$ i.e. the time change in the physical density. (Here $\frac{d}{dt}$ is the partial time derivative.). On the RHS, $\frac{d}{dy} \psi(y)$ is related to the change in spatial density $\psi(y) \psi(y)$ as one moves from one x point to another holding t constant. Both of these fluxes may be periodic leading to an overall periodic motion related to the fluxes (in addition to the second resonance of $\psi(y)$ which satisfies a time-independent type Schrodinger equation).

It has been argued in (3), that quantum mechanics makes use of two velocities $v(x)$ and $u(x)/m = 1/m [d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$. It seems that the two equations arising involve each of these velocities. It is interesting that for this case, $W_0(y)$, the ground state of the oscillator type equation ((3)) with $y=x + b(t)$ couples with a flux equation ((4)) to create an overall new ground state $\exp(i y d/dt b) W_0(y)$ for the system with potential: $.5kx^2 + x f(t)$. If one adds phonons, one may excite $W_0(y)$ to higher levels, but this changes its space and time flux, which in turn changes equation ((4)) physically, even though both sides cancel.

Energy Considerations

The energy of the overall oscillator plus $x f(t)$ system should be given by:

$$\langle W(x,t) | H | W(x,t) \rangle \text{ (integrated over space)}$$

Here $W(x,t) = \exp(iEt) \exp(i b(t) y) W_a(y)$. Thus, the two exponential factors disappear under W^*W and only the energy of $W_a(y)$ is in question. $W_a(y)$, however, satisfies the time independent Schrodinger equation:

$$-1/2m d/dy d/dy W_a(y) + .5k y^2 W_a(y) = E W_a(y) \quad ((6))$$

Here E is actually $E_n = \sqrt{k/m} (n+.5)$ and $W_a(y) = W_{a,n}(y)$

This, however, does not include the full potential present. There are still pieces:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Integral } dx \quad .5k [b(t)b(t) + 2 b(t) y] W_a(y)W_a(y) + (y+b) f(t) W_a(y)W_a(y) \\ & = \quad b(t) f(t) 1 + .5k b(t)b(t) \quad ((7)) \end{aligned}$$

The terms with y vanish because one may transform $y=x-b$ and $dy=dx$ with the integration range from $-\infty$ to ∞ for a given t . These y terms are associated with the time-space flux equation ((4)). Thus, one is only left with pure time potential terms which do not correspond to a force because $F(x)=-d/dx V(x)$. These terms were canceled in ((3)) by using a transformation $\exp(i g(t))$. For a given t , the extra time dependent potential terms are a constant, so it is as if one is shifting the energy, it seems, but this shift changes from one time point to another.

$f(t)$ is linked to $b(t)$ by:

$$m d/dt d/dt b(t) = f(t) - k b(t)$$

Thus, it seems there is an extra time-dependent portion of energy ((7)) not associated with $E_n = \sqrt{k/m} (n + .5)$. This energy is like a space independent potential which changes in time. Interestingly, in the excited oscillator state case with only $V(x) = .5k x^2$ $W(x) = W_0(x)H_n(x)$, the energy E_1 related to the coupling of $W_0(x)$ and $H_n(x)$ represents kinetic energy which is also spatially independent.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems the time dependent case of a harmonic oscillator with an extra $x f(t)$ potential can be treated using ideas related to using $W(x) = W_0(x) H_n(x)$ where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state wavefunction. In such a case, one obtains two equations, a time-independent Schrodinger equation for $W_0(x)$ and an equation linking time flux $[d/dt W(x,t)]/W(x,t)$ to space flux $[d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$. In that case, $W(x,t) = \exp(iE_1 t) W(x)$ so time flux becomes $1/W(x) \exp(iE_1 t)$ and one obtains an eigenvalue equation. Thus, there are two resonances which combine.

For the oscillator with $x f(t)$ examined in this note, one may again try to equate time and space fluxes, using $W(x,t) = q(x,t)W(x)$. In this case, a transformation $y = x - b(t)$ has to be performed first so that $d/dt W(x,t)$ can be converted into a $d/dy W(y,t)$ term. The factor $q(x,t)$ in this case is $\exp[i y d/dt b(t)]$ so that the two fluxes cancel. Other terms linear in y remain linking part of the oscillator potential with part of $x f(t) = (y + b) f(t)$ (the y part). Then, y cancels leaving an equation linking $b(t)$ and $f(t)$. Pure time terms remain in the non-flux second equation (which resembles a Schrodinger equation for an oscillator), but these can be removed by using $\exp(i g(t))$ (a second transformation) as discussed above. In such a case, one obtains a time-dependent Schrodinger type resonance (although the one has $W(y)$ where $y = x - b(t)$) and a second equation linking time and spatial flux. Thus, the two velocities $v(x)$ and $u(x)/m = [d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$ seem to lead to two processes in this example as well as in the regular oscillator excited state case. Although the problem of the oscillator with $x f(t)$ has already been solved mathematically in the literature (1), we have tried to present physical arguments in this note, especially linked to time and space flux.

References

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